

δ_{NCS} modes, respectively, suggesting N-bonded thiocyanate ion¹⁷. The intense band at $\sim 2000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a weaker band at $\sim 1280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching respectively of azide ion were observed, indicating its terminal coordination¹⁸. The 950 cm^{-1} band was attributed to $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ ¹⁹. The coordination of thiocyanate and azide ion in the sixth coordination position lowers $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ from $\sim 990 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$, $\text{VO}(\text{ox})_2$ and $\text{VO}(\text{pyca})_2$ to $\sim 950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the present complexes. Lowering of the $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ suggests coordination of thiocyanate and azide ion *trans* to V=O group in the complexes²⁰.

Electronic spectra of the complexes showed two bands, one transition is around 12000 cm^{-1} due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$, d_{zx} (ν_1) and the other around 16000 cm^{-1} due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ (ν_2).

The observed data are in conformity with a distorted octahedral structure²¹⁻²² for vanadium(IV).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. D. V. Ramana Rao for his keen interest in this work and to Prof. Somnath Misra, Principal, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela for facilities. The authors extend their thanks to the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for recording ir spectra.

References

1. J. SELBIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 153.
2. P. C. STEWART and A. L. PORTE, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 1661.
3. M. PASQUALI, F. MARCHETTI, G. FLORIANI and S. MERLINO, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 139.
4. C. E. MANNIX and A. P. ZIPP, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 59.
5. T. G. F. HUDSON, "Vanadium Toxicology and Biological Significance", Elsevier, New York, 1964.
6. K. M. PUROHIT and D. V. R. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 863.
7. K. M. PUROHIT and D. V. R. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 520.
8. S. MISHRA and K. M. PUROHIT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, 27, 78.
9. T. MOELLER, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, 5, 113.
10. R. C. AGGARWAL, R. BALA and R. L. PRASAD, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 568.
11. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longmans, London, 1962.
12. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.
13. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 406.
14. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd ed., Wiley, New York, 1978, p. 247.
15. R. C. CHARLES, M. FREISER, R. FRIEDEL, L. E. HILLAND and W. D. JOHNSTON, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1956, 8, 1.
16. G. W. A. FOWLES, R. W. MATHEWS and R. A. WALTON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1108.
17. J. L. BURMEISTER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 205; 1966, 3, 325.
18. K. C. DASH and CH. K. C. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 84.
19. A. N. SPECA, N. M. KARAYANIS and L. L. PYTLEWSKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1974, 9, 87.

20. J. J. R. FRANSTO DA SILVA and R. WOOTON, *Chem. Commun.*, 1969, 421.
21. H. J. STOKLOSA, J. R. WASOON and B. J. MURCORMIC, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 592.
22. R. K. AGARWAL and G. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 926.
23. B. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, 26, 850.

Precipitate based Selective Ion Sensitive Membrane Electrodes for Tripositive Chromium and Aluminium

RAJESH CHANDRA MISRA**

and

M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA*

Chemical Laboratories, Allahabad University, Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 8 August 1988, accepted 20 September 1988

NO commercial ion selective electrode for Cr^{III} and Al^{III} ions is available. Both the ions are usually determined by indirect potentiometry in which a different electrode is used, e.g. copper(II) ISEs are being used¹ for the determination of Al^{III} . In this paper we report the electrodes for these tripositive ions which are based on the dithiozone precipitate of the respective ion as an electroactive material.

Experimental

Green coloured chromium(III) dithiozonate and ash coloured aluminium(III) dithiozonate precipitates were obtained by adding in dilute solutions of the salts of the respective metal ions, an ammonical solution of dithiozone². After washing and drying the precipitate, the master membrane with each precipitate was prepared by mixing the precipitate (100 mg) with epoxy resin (400 mg)³.

Preparation of electrodes: A small portion from each membrane was cut out and fixed at one end of the glass tube (o.d. 0.8 cm and i.d. 0.5 cm) with the help of Araldite. These tubes were filled with 0.1 M solution of CrCl_3 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, respectively. A saturated calomel electrode was inserted for electrical contact. A separate saturated calomel electrode was used as external reference electrode. The electrode systems can be represented as

SCE | 0.1 M $\text{M}^{\text{3+}}$ | membrane | sample | SCE

where, $\text{M} = \text{Cr}^{\text{3+}}$ or $\text{Al}^{\text{3+}}$. Before taking measurement the membrane of each electrode system was kept immersed for 6 days in 0.1 M solution of the respective ions.

Results and Discussion

Two separate sets of solution of CrCl_3 and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ were prepared in which the concentration

**Present address: Conservation Laboratory, Allahabad Museum, Allahabad.

NOTES

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Electrode	Lower detection limit M	Slope of response curve mV	Response time s	Working pH range	Life of electrode month
1.	Cr ^{III} ISE	1×10^{-6}	20	15	2.8 - 7.6	8
2.	Al ^{III} ISE	5×10^{-7}	20	10	8.2 - 10.8	10

TABLE 2—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS FOR DIFFERENT CATIONS

Sl. no.	Electrode	Ions										
		Ce ³⁺	La ³⁺	Bi ³⁺	Sb ³⁺	Fe ³⁺	Cr ³⁺	As ³⁺	Al ³⁺	Zr ⁴⁺	Pb ²⁺	Hg ²⁺
1.	Cr ^{III} ISE	0.010	0.005	0.050	0.050	0.005	—	0.005	0.001	0.0050	0.97	0.18
2.	Al ^{III} ISE	0.005	0.001	0.005	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.001	—	0.0005	0.00	0.00

was varied in the range from 1×10^{-2} to 1×10^{-7} M and the potential was recorded with respective ion-selective electrode with the help of a Philips PR 9405 M pH meter at room temperature ($23 \pm 1^\circ$). The response of each electrode was plotted against the concentration of the respective ion in a semilog graph paper. In case of Cr^{III} electrode a linear response was observed down to the concentration of 1×10^{-6} M and for the Al^{III} electrode the value was 5×10^{-7} M. Other properties like response time, pH range, age of the membrane of all the three electrodes was determined (Table 1). The selectivity coefficients were determined by the mixed solution method⁴ (Table 2).

Titration of Cr^{III}, Al^{III} ion against phosphate ion :

Both Cr^{III} and Al^{III} give precipitate with orthophosphate ion and precipitation titration between these species can be monitored with a suitable sensor^{5,6}. For the titration of the above metal ions against phosphate ion, standard solutions of the salts of Cr^{III} and Al^{III} (0.01 M) and Na₂HPO₄ (0.01 M) were prepared. The solution (5 ml) was diluted to 20 ml by double-distilled water and its electrode potential measured with the respective ISE. The solution was then titrated against Na₂HPO₄

solution and after every addition of 0.1 ml Na₂HPO₄ solution, the electrode potential was noted. The potential values were plotted against the volume of Na₂HPO₄ solution consumed in titration. A sharp rise in the titration curve was observed to occur near the end-point (Fig. 1).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to State Council of Science and Technology, Lucknow, for financial assistance.

References

1. L. SUCHA and M. SUCHAREK, *Anal. Lett.*, 1978, 3, 613.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", E.L.B.S., London, 1969.
3. R. C. MISRA and M. C. CHATTOPADHYAYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, 27, 1011.
4. G. J. MOODY and J. D. R. THOMAS, *Talanta*, 1971, 18, 1251.
5. R. P. BUCK, *Anal. Chem.*, 1966, 38, 973.
6. W. S. SALIC, *Int. Laboratory*, 1984, 14, 50.

Fig. 1. Plots of potential against volume of Na₂HPO₄ solution.

Photocyclisation of *trans*-Stilbene

N. SAHOO* and R. J. GALAGALI

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 17 March 1988, revised 26 August 1988, accepted 23 September 1988

THE *trans* ⇌ *cis* isomerisation of stilbene with photosensitisers take place by the transfer of energy of sensitisers to stilbene during excitation under the uv irradiation¹. The photocyclisation and photoisomerisation of *trans*-stilbene has been discussed under nitrogen laser. The laser irradiation diminishes the time period of irradiation and gives maximum yield than that of the normal uv irradiation.